

Analysing the Perceptions of Secondary School Religious Culture and Ethics (DKAB) Teachers About Measurement and Evaluation Process: Izmir Case

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ABSTRACT :The course on Religious Culture and Ethics (DKAB) is a significant subject in Turkey's education system, aiming to help students understand religious culture and internalize moral values. DKAB lessons are designed to support students' abilities to conduct research, solve problems, and make sense of life while considering individual differences. The curriculum prioritizes meaningful learning over superficial memorization, based on the constructivist learning model. A unique approach tailored to DKAB has been adopted in the measurement and evaluation process. The Ministry of National Education recommends incorporating alternative and student-centered measurement and evaluation techniques instead of standardized methods in DKAB classes, promoting diversity and flexibility in the process. The use of methods such as performance tasks, open-ended questions, student portfolios, and projects is encouraged, enabling students to demonstrate their knowledge and skills. This study examines the perceptions of DKAB teachers regarding measurement and evaluation processes in public schools in İzmir. Data were collected from 115 teachers through snowball sampling. The study considers participants' gender, age, seniority, education level, and whether they have received training in measurement and evaluation. The findings reveal that teachers' perceptions vary based on factors such as gender, age, seniority, education level, and training status. In particular, younger and less experienced teachers were found to have more positive perceptions, while the diversity of perceptions decreased with increased seniority. These findings highlight the importance of planning professional development programs for teachers and improving measurement and evaluation processes.

KEYWORDS: Education, Measurement, Evaluation, DKAB, İzmir.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is defined as a long-term and systematic process that brings about desired behavioural changes in individuals. This process aims at the development of the individual in cognitive, affective and psychomotor areas. Instruction is a sub-component of the education process and involves the planning, implementation and evaluation of various learning activities in order to achieve the target behaviours. Instruction plays a supporting and guiding role in the individual's learning process of the activities carried out in line with a specific learning goal. In this context, measurement and evaluation in education is the systematic determination and analysis of the knowledge, skills, attitudes and behaviours gained by students during the learning process and the use of these results to provide feedback on the educational process. Measurement is the process of converting an observable performance or behaviour in education into a numerical or qualitative value. Evaluation is the process of making decisions based on these measurement results. Assessment is not only limited to the determination of student achievement, but also includes the effectiveness of educational programmes and the quality of the teaching process.

In the Turkish education system, the Religious Culture and Moral Knowledge (DKAB) course aims to provide students with the skills to recognise religious culture, internalise moral values and act with ethical principles in social life. The course is not only limited to teaching religious knowledge but also contributes to the spiritual, moral and social development of students. The curriculum includes a wide range of subjects such as religion and religious culture, moral philosophy, values education, religion-society relationship and morality. Within this framework, students are taught basic values such as tolerance, understanding, ethical decision-making and social responsibility.

The DKAB curriculum is shaped by the constructivist learning model and student-centred approaches. Meaningful learning in the curriculum aims to create an environment where students can conduct research, solve problems and support their individual development. Alternative methods are adopted in measurement and evaluation processes. In this process, it is recommended to emphasise performance-based assessment techniques that take into account student differences and encourage cooperation and sharing. In addition, it is emphasised to create an innovative and democratic learning environment that supports the individual development of students.

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1. Measurement in Education

Measurement in education is the expression of the knowledge, skills, attitudes and behaviours gained by students during their learning processes with numerical or qualitative values according to certain criteria (Şahin, 2018). Measurement, which provides concrete data about students' learning outcomes and the success of teaching processes, is also defined as the process of systematically collecting information in education. This process has an important role in the objective evaluation of student performance and the development of teaching activities (Turgut & Baykul, 2021). On the other hand, measurement contributes to the objective evaluation of the outputs obtained in educational processes and helps teachers to improve their teaching methods. The validity and reliability of the measurement tools used in the evaluation of students' learning processes are of great importance in terms of reflecting both individual learning levels and the overall quality of education (Sarı, 2020).

The main purpose of measurement in education is to determine the learning levels of students, the effectiveness of teaching processes and the success of educational programmes (Karasar, 2018). In this context, measurement is carried out to evaluate student achievement, to provide feedback to teachers to improve teaching processes and to determine the extent to which educational programmes achieve their goals. In addition, it enables the identification of deficiencies and strengths in the education system, optimisation of teaching methods and monitoring the individual development of students (Mutluer, 2015).

Measurement in education has a vital role in accurately determining student achievement, increasing the effectiveness of teaching processes and developing educational programmes. Reliable and valid measurement tools provide feedback at every stage of the educational process by objectively revealing students' learning levels (Güler, 2011). At the same time, measurement provides teachers with the opportunity to identify students' strengths and weaknesses and to improve their teaching processes accordingly. Another factor that increases the importance of measurement in education is that it provides students with the opportunity to understand their individual learning processes and improve themselves (Turgut & Baykul, 2021).

Measurement process in education includes various methods such as written exams, oral exams, performance assessments, observations and portfolios. Measurement not only determines the achievements of students, but also evaluates the effectiveness of educational programmes, teaching materials and teaching strategies (Yurtçu, 2022). Measurement tools in education are used in a wide range from monitoring individual achievement to evaluating group achievement (Başol et al., 2013). This process is carried out by both quantitative (numerical data) and qualitative (observation and interpretation) methods and the measurement process can be done in various ways.

Direct Measurement

Direct measurement is a measurement method that assesses a certain skill, knowledge or behaviour of students in a context where these competencies are directly observable and measurable. In this method, it is based on the student performing a task or performance personally and directly observing this performance in line with the determined criteria (Aydın & Kaşlı, 2019). Direct measurement means evaluating the performances of students in real life and measuring these performances through observation (Arıkan, 2018).

Direct measurement is a type of measurement made by observing the moment or process in which that performance is realised, rather than measuring the student's performance indirectly. For example, observing a student's process of solving a maths problem, directly listening to a student read a text while assessing reading skills, or observing a student's social skills during group activities are examples of direct measurement method (Köse, 2021). This method is frequently used especially in skill-based courses and is considered as an effective tool in measuring students' cognitive, psychomotor and affective skills (Doğan, 2020). The first of some advantages of direct measurement is the observation of actual performance. Direct measurement offers the opportunity to evaluate students' actual performance. In this way, it can be observed how effectively the student fulfils a certain task or skill. Secondly, comprehensive feedback can be provided. Direct assessment allows for immediate feedback at each stage of the observed performance. This helps students to better understand their strengths and weaknesses in the learning process. Thirdly, it is possible to make a qualified evaluation. Direct observation of the student makes the evaluation process more qualified and meaningful. Monitoring performance provides the opportunity to evaluate not only the results but also the process (Turgut & Baykul, 2021; Çıkrıkçı Demirtaşlı, 2014). However, direct measurement in education also has some disadvantages. Firstly, it requires time and resources. Direct measurement may require more time and resources for the evaluation of observed performances. Especially in large groups of students in traditional written exams, it can be quite time-consuming to evaluate the performance of each student with this method. Secondly, there may be observer bias. Since it is a method based on direct observation of performance, the subjectivity of the observer may affect the evaluation process. Therefore, it is of great importance that the observer is careful and objective (Tan, 2016; Karip, 2015).

In general, direct assessment has an important place in education as a comprehensive and meaningful assessment method that allows students to observe their real life skills and performances. Since it provides the opportunity to observe students' knowledge and skills in a concrete way, it provides a development-oriented evaluation process for both teachers and students.

Indirect Measurement

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Indirect measurement is a method of measuring a student's knowledge, skill or competence based on indicators or signs of this skill rather than direct observation. Students' knowledge and skills are measured indirectly, i.e. without direct observation, through instruments such as tests, questionnaires or examinations. In this method, indirect indicators of performance are evaluated, not the performance itself (Doğan, 2020). Indirect measurement is a method that is carried out by analysing indirect indicators of performance or knowledge without directly observing the student's performance or knowledge level. This method is used in cases where students cannot directly demonstrate a certain skill or knowledge area, but the existence of that knowledge or skill can be determined through different indicators (Güler, 2011).

Three types of methods are generally used in indirect measurement. The first one is tests and exams. Without directly observing the knowledge of the student, it is evaluated through written or multiple-choice exams. The second is questionnaire applications. It is used to indirectly measure whether the student has a certain attitude or opinion. The third is self-assessment and peer assessment forms. These are tools used to indirectly measure students' perceptions and evaluations of their own learning processes (Bahar, 2022). Indirect measurement in education has three important advantages. Firstly, it is time and resource efficient. Indirect assessment methods offer easy, fast and economical solutions that can be applied in large groups of students. When short-term exams or tests are used to evaluate student performance, teachers can assess students' knowledge levels in a wide range (Turgut & Baykul, 2021). Secondly, standardisation can be achieved. Indirect measurement tools such as tests and exams can be prepared in line with certain standards and can be applied equally for large groups. This can increase the comparability of the results (Doğan, 2020). Thirdly, it is possible to evaluate the cognitive domain. Indirect measurement methods are particularly effective tools for assessing students' knowledge and conceptual abilities. Multiple-choice tests and written exams play an important role in assessing students' performance at the cognitive level (Çıkrıkçı Demirtaşlı, 2014). However, indirect measurement in education also has disadvantages. Firstly, there may be a lack of direct performance observation. In indirect measurement methods, students' real life performances or behaviours are not directly observed. This provides limited information about the extent to which students can put their knowledge and skills into practice (Tan, 2016). Secondly, validity issues may arise. Indirect measurement methods may include limitations in terms of validity, as they give results based on performances that are not directly observed. The fact that a student gets a high grade in an exam does not mean that that knowledge can be applied in real life (Karip, 2015). The last one may be the risk of superficial evaluation. Especially in multiple-choice tests, students may often find superficial learning sufficient and higher-level skills such as critical thinking or creative problem solving may be ignored (Şahin, 2021).

In general, indirect assessment is a frequently used method in education to measure knowledge and skills quickly and efficiently in large groups of students. However, the fact that it does not include direct performance observation carries the risk that the results obtained with this method cannot fully reflect student achievement. Although indirect measurement methods in education are particularly effective in the assessment of cognitive learning areas, they may not be sufficient in the assessment of psychomotor and affective areas.

Evaluation

Assessment is the process of measuring and analysing students' progress in the learning process, knowledge levels, skills and attitudes as part of the educational process (Gürsoy, 2017). Assessment not only determines the academic achievement of students, but also provides the opportunity to review the effectiveness of curricula, teaching methods and materials. Assessment in education plays an important role in the decision-making processes of educators and institutions (Göçer, 2018). The main purpose of evaluation in education is to increase the effectiveness of the learning process. The first purpose of assessment is to support the learning process. By determining the strengths and weaknesses of students, it is possible to improve the learning process and intervene when necessary (Turgut & Baykul, 2021). Within the scope of determining the goals, it helps to determine the goals that students should achieve and to evaluate the level of achievement of these goals. In addition, by providing feedback to students and teachers about the learning process, it encourages continuous development, helps to provide data for determining educational policies, reviewing the curriculum and developing teaching strategies (Güler, 2011). There are four different dimensions of evaluation in education. The first is Formal Assessment. These are formal assessments made with standardised tools such as written exams, projects and tests. These assessments are usually expressed in numerical data and determine the student's learning level (Çıkrıkçı Demirtaş, 2014). The second is informal assessment. These are assessments carried out with informal tools such as observations, student participation, discussions and group work. Such assessments provide the opportunity to observe students' behaviours and interactions in the process (Tekindal, 2020). As a result, assessment in education is a critical process for monitoring students' learning processes, developing teaching strategies and improving the quality of education. Assessment, which is carried out by both formal and informal methods, plays an important role in the decision-making processes of educators. In this context, diversification and effective application of assessment methods will enrich students' learning experiences.

Measurement and Evaluation in Religious Culture and Moral Knowledge Course

Religious Culture and Moral Knowledge (DKAB) course is an important course in the Turkish education system, which is included in the curriculum in order for students to understand religious culture and internalise moral values (Konaklı et al., 2021). This course

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is not only limited to the transfer of religious knowledge, but also aims to equip students with social values and ethical principles as individuals. The importance of the Religious Culture and Moral Knowledge course stems from the fact that it plays an important role in the spiritual, moral and social development of individuals (Dođru, 2024). Religious Culture and Moral Knowledge course includes the effects of religion on the individual and society, the development of moral values and how these values are reflected in social life. The curriculum covers various subjects (MEB, 2018):

- Religion and Religious Culture: Students are provided with information about different religions and belief systems in order to develop tolerance and understanding.
- Moral Philosophy: Lessons on the definition, importance and effects of morality on individuals are taught.
- Values Education: Individuals are informed about social values, ethical principles and moral responsibilities (Özdemir, 2021).
- Religion and Society: Interactions between religion and society help individuals to understand their role in social life.
- Morality: Morality is a system that helps individuals distinguish between right and wrong. This course emphasises moral principles to enable students to make moral judgements and ethical decisions.

DKAB courses aim to raise individuals who can solve problems, conduct research and make sense of the complexities of life by taking individual differences into consideration. The vision of the DKAB programme points to the search for meaning by emphasising the importance of the role of religion in making sense of life. The expression of living together in diversity emphasises the existence of multiple meanings rather than a single meaning. In addition, the vision document shows that meaning stems from national, spiritual and moral values (Konaklı et al., 2021; MEB, 2018).

When the basic philosophy and general objectives of the DKAB curriculum are examined, it is understood that it is based on approaches such as multiple intelligence, student-centred learning and competency-based education that support the constructivist learning model. Among the basic skills emphasised for students are active participation, teacher guidance and personal development. Students are expected to seek knowledge along with the search for meaning. The necessity of providing an environment in which students can conduct research, make discoveries, solve problems and share and discuss their solutions and approaches is emphasised. Providing meaningful learning instead of superficial memorisation is set as a primary goal. The curriculum aims for students to integrate their own interpretations of knowledge and their thoughts on the meaning of life (Konaklı et al., 2021; MEB, 2018).

- Measurement and evaluation in the DKAB course has its own unique characteristics compared to other courses. The Ministry of National Education recommends the use of alternative methods instead of standard types of assessment and evaluation in the GCE teaching programmes. It is possible to list these suggestions as follows (MEB, 2010):
- Avoiding evaluating students by using prejudiced labels such as hardworking, lazy or naughty.
- Carrying out the learning process in a democratic learning environment that encourages sharing, co-operation and solidarity among students instead of competition.
- The ability of teachers to create innovative and useful learning environments for the benefit of students.
- Providing a variety of assessment opportunities for students to demonstrate their knowledge and skills.
- The predominant use of student-centred assessment methods and techniques.
- Using more than one method together when assessing students' achievements.
- Including various question types such as multiple choice, short answer and matching questions in exams.
- Including open-ended questions, student product files, observation forms, performance tasks, posters and projects within the framework of performance-based assessments.
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In 2018, MEB made some new recommendations to guide teachers on measurement and evaluation in the DKAB course. In the new proposal, it is stated that there are no definite limits in the measurement and evaluation process to be applied in the DKAB course and that teachers can use alternative methods in line with the general principles and objectives. Accordingly, it is recommended to pay attention to the following in the measurement and evaluation process to be applied in the DKAB course (MEB, 2018):

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- Recognising that people are different from each other and that uniform measurement and evaluation is not appropriate in this context,
- Acting with the understanding of maximum diversity and flexibility in the measurement and evaluation process,
- Measurement and evaluation activities are compatible with all components of the curriculum,
- The preferred assessment and evaluation methods and techniques comply with academy standards.

SUMMARY OF LITERATURE

Şimşek (2022). He analysed the attitudes of DKAB teachers towards measurement and evaluation. As a result of the study in which 341 DKAB teachers participated, it was found that there was a significant difference between the attitudes of DKAB teachers towards measurement and evaluation according to gender, formation training status, graduated faculty, length of service and type of school where they worked; and that the attitudes of those who received training on measurement and evaluation differed from those who did not.

Cingöz and Akyürek (2021) analysed the opinions of DKAB teachers about the contribution of assessment and evaluation techniques to critical thinking education. As a result of semi-structured interviews with 12 DKAB teachers working in Kayseri province, it was found that 'most of the teachers' questions in the exams were at the level of comprehension; they did not include questions at the level of 'application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation' that could contribute to students' more effective use of critical thinking skills; they could not give performance homework that could contribute to critical thinking education and could not evaluate them according to appropriate criteria'.

Karbeyaz (2018) analysed the level of use of alternative assessment and evaluation (AÖD) techniques by DKAB teachers. As a result of the study in which 129 DKAB teachers participated, it was found that DKAB teachers used open-ended question, concept map, oral presentation, project, observation and performance more frequently than other AÖD techniques; their use of AÖD techniques did not differ, and they used oral presentation, observation, open-ended question, concept map techniques more frequently than other techniques.

Yıldız and Genç (2016) analysed the levels of secondary school DKAB teachers' use of alternative assessment and evaluation techniques and the problems they encountered.

As a result of their study conducted with the participation of DKAB teachers, they found that DKAB teachers used performance, project, observation and concept map techniques at a higher rate than other techniques. In addition, they also found that the level of use of the techniques according to the characteristics of gender, age and graduated programme of DKAB teachers was significantly affected (Yıldız & Genç, 2016).

Işıkdoğan (2014) analysed the perceptions of DKAB teachers towards constructivist assessment and evaluation approach in Diyarbakır and Şanlıurfa samples. As a result of the study, it was found that male DKAB teachers had a more positive view of the constructivist approach than female DKAB teachers.

Gündoğdu (2012) investigated the measurement tools preferred by the DKAB teachers. As a result of the study in which 557 DKAB teachers working in Istanbul province participated, it was determined that DKAB teachers preferred traditional measurement tools more than alternative measurement tools and the most preferred measurement tool was performance tasks.

Çakmak (2011) analysed alternative measurement and evaluation (AÖD) techniques and the level of teachers' use of them. As a result of the study in which 250 DKAB teachers participated, it was found that there was no significant relationship between the level of use of alternative assessment and evaluation techniques and teachers' gender, seniority, graduated programme, average class size and the number of class hours per week, and that those who received training on alternative assessment and evaluation techniques used alternative assessment and evaluation techniques more.

1. METHODOLOGY

Purpose of the Research

The main purpose of this study is to examine the perceptions of Religious Culture and Moral Knowledge (DKAB) teachers working at the secondary education level about the measurement and evaluation process. Within the scope of the study, the perceptions of Religious Culture and Ethics teachers about the methods they use such as self-assessment, peer and group assessment, observation assessment, oral presentation assessment, project assessment and product file assessment were investigated. Thus, it is aimed to reveal how teachers' measurement and evaluation approaches are shaped and the effects of these approaches on student achievement. On the other hand, it is thought that this study has a unique value in terms of understanding the attitudes of religious studies teachers in measurement and evaluation processes. In particular, knowing how assessment and evaluation methods such as self-assessment, peer assessment and project assessment within the framework of '21st Century Skills' are perceived by the DKAB teachers can be a guide for making assessment and evaluation practices more effective in DKAB education. In addition, it is thought that the study will contribute to the development of both the teaching and evaluation processes of the course by understanding how the academic and spiritual dimensions of the religious studies courses are associated with the measurement and evaluation processes. On the other

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hand, since the use of qualified measurement and evaluation methods in DKAB education will increase the efficiency of teaching processes as well as student achievement, this study aims to reveal important findings that can guide teachers' professional development and educational policies.

RESEARCH MODEL

In this study, it is aimed to examine the perceptions of measurement and evaluation of DKAB teachers working at secondary education level in terms of different variables. In this context, the study is a quantitative study with relational survey model. Relational survey model is used in many fields such as educational sciences, social sciences, psychology and economics. The Relational Survey Model is a descriptive research model used to examine the relationship between variables in research (Karasar, 2016). In this model, the relationship or co-change between two or more variables is examined and the correlation between them is tried to be revealed. The relational survey model is used to determine the direction and degree of relationships between variables, but this relationship is not in the context of cause and effect, but only to define existing relationships (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013).

Sample of the Research

The population of the study consists of Religious Culture and Moral Knowledge (DKAB) teachers working in public schools in Izmir province. However, since reaching the whole population has great difficulties in terms of both time and cost, it was necessary to select a sample in the study. In this context, snowball sampling method was preferred. Snowball sampling is a practical and effective method that is widely used especially in cases where it is difficult to completely define a specific target group. This method is based on the expansion of the participant network by starting from the first participants that the researcher can reach and suggesting other people with similar characteristics in their environment (Karasar, 2016). This is especially advantageous in cases where access to a specific professional group, such as DKAB teachers, is required. Information about the sample of the study is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Demographic Distribution *

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* Proportional distribution of the respondents according to their qualifications.

As can be seen in Figure 1, in the gender distribution of the participants, the ratio of males was determined as 43.5% and the ratio of females as 56.5%, and the total number of participants was recorded as 115. In the distribution according to age groups, 11.3% of the participants were between 26-35 years old, 53.0% were between 36-45 years old, 28.7% were between 46-55 years old and 7.0% were 56 years old and above. The total of these groups reached 115 people. At the seniority level, 14.8% of the participants have 1-5 years of seniority, 28.7% have 11-15 years of seniority, 20.0% have 16-20 years of seniority, 16.5% have 21 years and above and 20.0% have 6-10 years of seniority. The total number of people in seniority groups was expressed as 115. According to

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the level of education, 82.6% of the participants have bachelor's degree, while 17.4% of the participants have postgraduate degree. The total number of education levels also includes 115 people. Participants who have received training on measurement and evaluation are 63.5% and those who have not received training are 36.5%, and the total number of participants in this category is 115.

Obtaining and Analysing the Research Data

In obtaining the research data, a questionnaire was applied to the participants. As a data collection tool, the scale of 'DKAB Measurement and Evaluation Perceptions Attitude Scale' (DÖDAÖ) developed by Rençber (2010) consisting of 6 dimensions and a total of 55 questions was used. Descriptive Statistics, one of the analyses used in the study, was used to summarise the demographic characteristics of the participants (frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation). These analyses form the basis for defining the general structure of the sample. Intergroup Comparison (t-Test and ANOVA) was used to compare the perception averages of different groups according to gender, age, seniority, education level and assessment and evaluation training status. These tests were preferred to determine the significant differences between the groups. Reliability analyses (Cronbach's Alpha and McDonald's Omega) were used to evaluate the internal consistency of the scales and sub-dimensions. These analyses were conducted to test the reliability and validity of the scales. For this study, validity and reliability tests were applied to the scale (Table 2).

According to Figure 2, the overall scale reliability has a very high reliability level with both Cronbach's Alpha (0.882) and McDonald's Omega (0.905) values. When the sub-dimensions were analysed, the Cronbach's Alpha value of the 'Self-Assessment Perceptions' dimension showed a high reliability with 0.807, while the McDonald's Omega value remained at a relatively lower level with 0.707. While the Cronbach's Alpha value of the 'Peer and Group Evaluation Perceptions' dimension was within the acceptable limit with 0.700, the McDonald's Omega value showed a lower reliability with 0.560. In the 'Observation Evaluation Perceptions' dimension, Cronbach's Alpha value was 0.792, McDonald's Omega value was 0.720 and this sub-dimension was found to have a good reliability in general. In the 'Perceptions of Oral Presentation Evaluation' dimension, Cronbach's Alpha value shows a borderline reliability with 0.662, while McDonald's Omega value reflects a lower reliability level with 0.568. In the 'Perceptions of Project Evaluation' dimension, both Cronbach's Alpha (0.325) and McDonald's Omega (0.284) values were found to be quite low and at a weak level in terms of reliability. On the other hand, Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.720 and McDonald's Omega value of 0.675 in the 'Product File Evaluation Perceptions' dimension provided an acceptable level of reliability. From the table, it can be concluded that the reliability levels vary among the sub-dimensions in general and there is a need for improvement in some sub-dimensions.

RESULTS

The findings related to the perceptions of the DKAB teachers participating in the study on self-assessment in the measurement and evaluation process are presented in Figure 3.

1. Gender and Self-Assessment Perceptions: It is seen that there is a weak positive relationship between gender variable and some items. For example: There is a correlation value of 0.21 between the item ‘It helps students discover their talents.’ and gender. On the other hand, there is a significant negative correlation of -0.29 between the item ‘Self-assessment does not contribute to recognising students’ and gender. This may indicate that male and female teachers approach some self-assessment items differently. However, in general, the effect of gender is weak.

2. Age and Self-Assessment Perceptions: Age variable shows significant negative correlations with some items: There is a correlation value of -0.41 between the item ‘It increases the motivation level of students.’ and age. Similarly, there is a negative correlation of -0.22 between the item ‘It helps students to discover their talents’ and age. These results may indicate that older teachers show a lower tendency towards some self-evaluation items.

3. Seniority and Self-Assessment Perceptions: Seniority has a positive correlation with a few items. There is a 0.19 correlation between the item ‘It increases the motivation level of the students.’ and seniority. Also, there is a positive correlation of 0.12 between the item ‘It enables students to control their behaviours’ and seniority. This may indicate that more senior teachers have a more positive approach to certain self-assessment items. However, it should be taken into consideration that the diversity of perceptions decreases as seniority increases.

4. Education and Self-Assessment Perceptions: There are weak positive correlations between education level and some items. There is a correlation of 0.19 between the item ‘It enables students to control their behaviours.’ and education. On the other hand, there is a very low correlation of 0.07 between the item ‘It increases the motivation level of students’ and education. It can be seen that teachers with higher education levels tend to have a slightly more positive approach to self-evaluation processes.

5. Status of Receiving Measurement and Value Education: It is seen that teachers who received measurement and value education approached some items more positively. There is a positive correlation of 0.08 between this variable and the item ‘It helps students discover their talents.’ There is a significant negative correlation of -0.35 with the item ‘Self-assessment does not contribute to recognising students’. These results show that receiving measurement and value education can have positive effects on teacher perceptions.

In general, although the effect of demographic variables on ‘Self-Assessment Perceptions’ is at a low level, there are some significant relationships. When we look at the prominent findings, as the age increases, a lower tendency is observed for some self-evaluation items (e.g. ‘It increases the motivation level of students.’, correlation: -0.41). As seniority increased, a positive increase was observed in some items (e.g. ‘It enables students to control their behaviour’, correlation: 0.12). As for education and training status, it is seen that receiving measurement and value training has an effect on positive perceptions (e.g. ‘Self-assessment does not contribute to knowing the student.’, correlation: -0.35).

The findings related to the perceptions of the DKAB teachers participating in the research on Peer and Group Assessment in the measurement and evaluation process are presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Perception of Peer and Group Evaluation

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1. Gender and Peer and Group Evaluation Perceptions: There are generally weak correlations between gender variable and ‘Peer and Group Assessment Perceptions’. There is a correlation value of 0.15 between the item ‘It helps students get to know their friends’ and gender. On the other hand, there is a weak negative correlation of -0.10 between the item ‘Peer assessment does not contribute to getting to know the student’ and gender. It can be said that the effect of gender on this perception dimension is limited in general.

2. Age and Peer and Group Assessment Perceptions: There are significant negative correlations between age variable and some items in this perception dimension. There is a correlation value of -0.28 between the item ‘Students are directly involved in the evaluation process.’ and age. Similarly, there is a -0.21 negative correlation between the item ‘Students cannot be objective.’ and age. This may indicate that older teachers exhibit less positive approaches in peer and group assessment processes.

3. Seniority and Peer and Group Evaluation Perceptions: Seniority has a positive correlation with a few items. There is a positive correlation of 0.12 between the item ‘It helps students get to know their friends.’ and seniority. However, a negative correlation of -0.18 was observed between the item ‘Peer assessment does not contribute to getting to know students’ and seniority. It can be thought that more senior teachers make positive contributions to students’ peer and group assessment processes.

4. Education and Peer and Group Assessment Perceptions: There are generally weak correlations between education level and this perception dimension. There is a positive correlation of 0.14 between the item ‘Students are directly involved in the evaluation process.’ and education. However, there is a low negative correlation of -0.08 between the item ‘Students cannot be objective’ and education. It can be said that teachers with higher education levels perceive group assessment processes more positively.

5. Status of Receiving Measurement and Value Education: It was observed that teachers who received measurement and value education approached some items in this perception dimension more positively. There is a positive correlation of 0.20 between the item ‘It helps students to recognise their friends’ and this variable. However, there is a negative correlation of -0.12 with the item ‘It causes conflict among students’. This shows that receiving measurement and value education contributes positively to teachers’ peer and group assessment processes.

In general, the effect of demographic variables on ‘Peer and Group Evaluation Perceptions’ varies from weak to moderate. Considering the prominent findings, as age increases, lower perceptions are observed, especially in items such as ‘Students are directly involved in the evaluation process’ (correlation: -0.28). As seniority increases, a positive increase is observed in some items (e.g. ‘It helps students to recognise their friends’, correlation: 0.12). According to education and training status, it was observed that receiving measurement and value training made positive contributions to group evaluation processes (e.g. ‘It helps students to get to know their friends.’, correlation: 0.20).

Findings related to the perceptions of observation evaluation of the DKAB teachers participating in the study in the measurement and evaluation process are presented in Figure 5.

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Figure 5. Observation Assessment Perception

1. Gender and Observation Evaluation Perceptions: There are generally weak relationships between gender variable and ‘Observation Evaluation Perceptions’. There is a negative correlation of -0.15 between the item ‘Observation forms given in the appendix of the book are sufficient to evaluate students.’ and gender. A significant negative correlation of -0.38 was observed between the item ‘Observation does not contribute to recognising students’ and gender. These results show that female and male teachers exhibit limited but different approaches in their perception of observation assessment processes.

2. Age and Observation Evaluation Perceptions: There are significant correlations between age variable and some items. There is a positive correlation of 0.35 between the item ‘It should be used to measure performance-based skills’ and age. However, there is a negative correlation of -0.22 between the item ‘Students’ behaviour cannot always be observed objectively’ and age. This shows that older teachers are more favourable towards performance-based measurement methods, but they may have difficulties in being objective in their observations.

3. Seniority and Observation Evaluation Perceptions: Seniority has a positive correlation with many items. There is a positive correlation of 0.25 between the item ‘Teachers should prepare observation forms themselves when needed.’ and seniority. However, there is a negative correlation of -0.20 between seniority and the item ‘There are difficulties in the evaluation of observation results’. These findings show that senior teachers are more positive in preparing observation forms themselves, but they perceive more difficulties in the evaluation of observation results.

4. Education and Observation Evaluation Perceptions: There are generally weak relationships between education level and the items in this perception dimension. There is a positive correlation of 0.19 between the item ‘It should be used to measure performance-based skills.’ and education level. There is a negative correlation of -0.20 between the item ‘Difficulties are experienced in the evaluation of observation results.’ and educational level. It can be said that teachers with higher education level have a more positive view of processes such as measuring performance-based skills.

5. Status of Measurement and Value Education: Teachers who have received measurement and value training have more positive approaches to observation and evaluation processes. There is a significant negative correlation of -0.47 between the item “Observation does not contribute to getting to know the student.” and having measurement training. A negative correlation of -0.43 was observed with the item “Observation is difficult to implement in crowded classes.” These results show that teachers who received measurement and value training perceive observation and evaluation processes more positively and contributively.

In general, the effect of demographic variables on “Observation Evaluation Perceptions” varies from weak to moderate. When we look at the prominent findings, it was observed that as age and seniority increased, teachers tended to support performance-based observations (e.g. “It should be used to measure performance-based skills.”, correlation: 0.35). There are significant differences between male and female teachers' perceptions of observations (e.g. “Observation does not contribute to knowing the student”, correlation: -0.38). In terms of education and training status, it is seen that receiving measurement and value education contributes positively to observation evaluation processes (e.g. “Observation does not contribute to knowing the student.”, correlation: -0.47).

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The findings related to the perceptions of the DKAB teachers participating in the research on Oral Presentation Evaluation in the assessment and evaluation process are presented in Figure 6.

1. Gender and Perceptions of Oral Presentation Evaluation: There are generally weak negative correlations between the gender variable and “Perceptions of Oral Presentation Assessment”. There is a -0.17 correlation between the item “It is an effective method to measure students' critical thinking skills.” and gender. There is a -0.27 correlation between the item “Oral presentation does not contribute to getting to know the student” and gender. These results show that there are slight differences between male and female teachers' perceptions of oral presentation processes.

2. Age and Perceptions of Oral Presentation Evaluation: There are significant negative correlations between age variable and this perception dimension in some items. There is a -0.35 correlation between age and the item “It is an effective method for evaluating students' performance.” There is a -0.23 correlation between the item “It becomes difficult to maintain discipline in the classroom during oral presentation.” and age. This indicates that older teachers tend to perceive oral presentation processes as less effective or problematic.

3. Seniority and Perceptions of Oral Presentation Evaluation: Seniority variable shows positive correlation with some items and negative correlation with some items. There is a positive correlation of 0.26 between the item “It allows to observe students' higher level knowledge and skills.” and seniority. However, there is a negative correlation of -0.41 between the item “It is difficult to prepare and apply measurement tools for oral presentation” and seniority. These results suggest that as seniority increases, teachers are more critical of the specific challenges of oral presentation (e.g., preparation of assessment tools), but more positive about the potential for observing higher level skills.

4. Education and Perceptions of Oral Presentation Evaluation: There are generally weak positive correlations between education level and items in this perception dimension. There is a 0.08 correlation between education and the item “It is an effective method to measure students' critical thinking skills.” There is a -0.05 correlation between the item “Oral presentation does not contribute to getting to know the student.” and education. It can be said that teachers with higher education levels have a slightly more positive approach to oral presentation processes.

5. Measurement and Value Education Status: There is a positive correlation in some items and a negative correlation in others. There is a strong positive correlation of 0.41 between the item “It is difficult to maintain discipline in the classroom during oral presentations.” and having received assessment training. A negative correlation of -0.40 was observed with the item “Oral presentation does not contribute to getting to know the student.” This shows that teachers who have received measurement and value training are more aware of the difficulties in oral presentation processes, but they have a more positive perception of the contribution of the process to getting to know the student.

In general, the effect of demographic variables on “Perceptions of Oral Presentation Evaluation” is limited but noteworthy. The main findings suggest that while older and more senior teachers may perceive more difficulties in the oral presentation process, they

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are more positive that the process is effective in observing students' skills (e.g. “It allows observing students' higher level knowledge and skills”, correlation: 0.26). There are different perceptions between male and female teachers, especially regarding the item “Oral presentation does not contribute to getting to know the student” (correlation: -0.27).

Teachers who received assessment and evaluation training were more aware of issues such as classroom discipline and had a more positive perception of the contribution of the process to getting to know the student (e.g. “It is difficult to maintain discipline in the classroom during oral presentations.”, correlation: 0.41).

The findings related to the perceptions of the DKAB teachers participating in the research on Project Evaluation in the measurement and evaluation process are presented in Figure 7.

1. Gender and Project Evaluation Perceptions: Significant relationships were observed between gender variable and “Perceptions of Project Evaluation” in some items. There is a strong positive correlation of 0.45 between the item “In group projects, each student should not be given the same success score.” and gender. However, there is a negative correlation of -0.39 between the item “It is difficult to score” and gender. This shows that there are significant differences between male and female teachers' perceptions of group projects.

2. Age and Project Evaluation Perceptions: There are generally weak or negative relationships between age and some items: There is a -0.24 negative correlation between age and the item “Scoring errors can be reduced by using the project evaluation scale.” However, there is a 0.12 positive correlation between the item “It is difficult for students to come together in group projects.” and age. It can be said that as age increases, teachers perceive more difficulties in the applicability of projects.

3. Seniority and Project Evaluation Perceptions: The seniority variable has positive correlations in some items and negative correlations in some items. There is a positive correlation of 0.21 between the item “In group projects, each student should not be given the same success score.” and seniority. However, there is a -0.34 negative correlation between the item “It is difficult for students to come together in group projects.” and seniority. While senior teachers may be more sensitive about fair scoring in projects, they may perceive more implementation difficulties in group projects.

4. Education and Project Evaluation Perceptions: There are generally weak correlations between education level and “Perceptions of Project Evaluation”. There is a positive correlation of 0.14 between education and the item “Scoring errors can be reduced by using the project evaluation scale.” However, there is a weak negative correlation of -0.05 between the item “The project does not contribute to getting to know the student” and education. As the level of education increases, perceptions towards projects may change more positively.

5. Status of Receiving Measurement and Value Education: The status of receiving measurement and value education shows significant relationships with project evaluation processes in some items. There is a positive correlation of 0.32 between this variable and the item “In group projects, each student should not be given the same success score.” However, there is a 0.16 positive correlation between the item “It is difficult for students to come together in group projects.” and receiving measurement training. These findings indicate that receiving measurement and value education can increase teachers' awareness of projects.

In general, the effect of demographic variables on “Perceptions of Project Evaluation” ranges from low to moderate. There are significant differences between male and female teachers in their perceptions of group projects (e.g. “Not all students should be given the same achievement score in group projects.”, correlation: 0.45). Older and more senior teachers perceived more

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implementation difficulties in group projects (e.g. “It is difficult for students to come together in group projects.”, age: 0.12, seniority: -0.34). It was observed that teachers who received measurement and evaluation training had positive attitudes towards projects (e.g. “In group projects, not every student should be given the same achievement score.”, correlation: 0.32).

The findings related to the perceptions of the DKAB teachers participating in the research on the Product File Evaluation in the measurement and evaluation process are presented in Figure 8.

1. Gender and Project Evaluation Perceptions: Significant relationships were observed between gender variable and “Perceptions of Project Evaluation” in some items. There is a strong positive correlation of 0.45 between the item “In group projects, each student should not be given the same success score.” and gender. However, there is a negative correlation of -0.39 between the item “It is difficult to score” and gender. This shows that there are significant differences between male and female teachers' perceptions of group projects.

2. Age and Project Evaluation Perceptions: There are generally weak or negative relationships between age and some items. There is a -0.24 negative correlation between age and the item “Scoring errors can be reduced by using the project evaluation scale.” However, there is a 0.12 positive correlation between the item “It is difficult for students to come together in group projects.” and age. It can be said that as age increases, teachers perceive more difficulties in the applicability of projects.

3. Seniority and Project Evaluation Perceptions: The seniority variable has positive correlations in some items and negative correlations in some items. There is a positive correlation of 0.21 between the item “In group projects, each student should not be given the same success score.” and seniority. However, there is a -0.34 negative correlation between the item “It is difficult for students to come together in group projects.” and seniority. While senior teachers may be more sensitive about fair scoring in projects, they may perceive more implementation difficulties in group projects.

4. Education and Project Evaluation Perceptions: There are generally weak correlations between education level and “Perceptions of Project Evaluation”. There is a positive correlation of 0.14 between education and the item “Scoring errors can be reduced by using the project evaluation scale.” However, there is a weak negative correlation of -0.05 between the item “The project does not contribute to getting to know the student” and education. As the level of education increases, perceptions towards projects may change more positively.

5. Status of Receiving Measurement and Value Education: The status of receiving measurement and value education shows significant relationships with project evaluation processes in some items. There is a positive correlation of 0.32 between this variable and the item “In group projects, each student should not be given the same success score.” However, there is a 0.16 positive correlation between the item “It is difficult for students to come together in group projects.” and receiving measurement training. These findings indicate that receiving measurement and value education can increase teachers' awareness of projects.

In general, the effect of demographic variables on “Perceptions of Project Evaluation” ranges from low to moderate. There are significant differences between male and female teachers in their perceptions of group projects (e.g. “Not all students should be given the same achievement score in group projects.”, correlation: 0.45). Older and more senior teachers perceived more

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implementation difficulties in group projects (e.g. “It is difficult for students to come together in group projects.”, age: 0.12, seniority: -0.34). It was observed that teachers who received measurement and evaluation training had positive attitudes towards projects (e.g. “In group projects, not every student should be given the same achievement score.”, correlation: 0.32).

RESULT

In this study, the research aims to examine the perceptions of the DKAB teachers working in public schools in Izmir province in measurement and evaluation processes. Within the scope of the study, snowball sampling was used as a sampling method and data were collected from 115 teachers. 43.5% of the participants were male and 56.5% were female. Demographic variables such as age groups, seniority, education level and the status of receiving assessment and evaluation training were taken into consideration. The results of the research can be summarized as follows:

The perceptions of the DKAB teachers participating in the study in the measurement and evaluation processes were evaluated with a detailed analysis in terms of demographic variables. In the analysis of self-assessment perceptions, the gender variable showed a weak positive relationship with some items. For example, a correlation value of 0.21 was found between the item “It helps students discover their talents” and gender. However, there was a significant negative correlation of -0.29 between the item “Self-assessment does not contribute to getting to know the student” and gender. This shows that there are certain differences between male and female teachers' perceptions of self-assessment processes. When the age variable was examined, a correlation of -0.41 was found between the item “It increases the motivation level of students.” and age, which showed that older teachers evaluated this process less positively. A positive correlation of 0.12 was found between the seniority variable and the item “It enables students to control their behaviors.” It was understood that positive perceptions increased in certain items as seniority increased. The level of education and the status of receiving assessment-value training made positive contributions by showing a -0.35 correlation with the item “Self-assessment does not contribute to knowing the student.”

In terms of Peer and Group Assessment Perceptions, gender had a weak effect on some items. For example, there was a 0.15 positive correlation between gender and the item “It helps students get to know their friends.” and a -0.10 negative correlation with the item “Peer assessment does not contribute to getting to know the student.” The age variable showed a correlation of -0.28 with the item “Students are directly involved in the evaluation process.” and -0.21 with the item “Students cannot be objective.” These findings indicate that as age increases, negative perceptions increase in peer and group assessment processes. A positive correlation of 0.12 was found between seniority and the item “It helps students get to know their friends” While the level of education showed a positive correlation of 0.14 with the item ‘Students are directly involved in the evaluation process.’, the status of receiving assessment-value education showed a positive correlation of 0.20 with the item “It helps students get to know their friends.”

In the context of Observation Evaluation Perceptions, the effect of gender is significant in some items. There was a -0.15 correlation with the item “The observation forms given in the appendix of the book are sufficient to evaluate the students.” and a -0.38 correlation with the item “Observation does not contribute to getting to know the student.” The age variable correlated 0.35 with the item “It should be used to measure performance-based skills.” and -0.22 with the item “Student behavior cannot always be observed objectively.” There was a positive correlation of 0.25 between the seniority variable and the item “Teachers should prepare observation forms themselves when needed.” The level of education showed a correlation of 0.19 with the item “Observation forms should be used to measure performance-based skills.” and the status of receiving measurement-value training showed a correlation of -0.47 with the item “Observation does not contribute to getting to know the student.”

In terms of Oral Presentation Evaluation Perceptions, gender correlated -0.17 with the item “It is an effective method to measure students' critical thinking skills.” and -0.27 with the item “Oral presentation does not contribute to knowing the student. The age variable showed a correlation of -0.35 with the item “It is an effective method for evaluating students' performance.” Seniority showed a positive correlation of 0.26 with the item “It allows observing students' higher level knowledge and skills.” Education level showed a correlation of 0.08 with the item “It is an effective method to measure students' critical thinking skills.” and the status of receiving assessment and evaluation training showed a correlation of 0.41 with the item “It becomes difficult to maintain discipline in the classroom during oral presentations.”

It was determined that gender correlated 0.45 with the item “In group projects, each student should not be given the same success score.” and -0.39 with the item “It is difficult to score.” on Project Evaluation Perceptions. The age variable showed a correlation of -0.24 with the item “Scoring errors can be reduced by using the project evaluation scale.” and seniority showed a correlation of 0.21 with the item “Each student should not be given the same success score in group projects.” The status of receiving measurement and value education showed a positive correlation of 0.32 with the item “Each student should not be given the same achievement score in group projects.”

In the context of Product File Evaluation Perceptions, it was determined that gender correlated 0.45 with the item “It is possible to determine the deficiencies of the students with the product file.” and -0.33 with the item “Product files do not contribute to getting to know the student.” The age variable showed a correlation of -0.33 with the item “The works to be included in the product file should be determined by the teacher beforehand.” and seniority showed a correlation of 0.22 with the item “In the evaluation made

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with product files, the student participates in the evaluation process at every stage.” The status of receiving measurement and value education showed a correlation of 0.33 with the item “The tools given in the program for the evaluation of product files are insufficient.”

Although the findings obtained in our research are compatible with the studies in the existing literature, they also contain some differences. In Şimşek's (2022) study, it was stated that gender and the status of receiving measurement-evaluation training created significant differences in the attitudes of RCES teachers. In our findings, it was observed that there was a more positive tendency in the perceptions of teachers who received assessment and evaluation training, but this difference remained at a limited level. In terms of gender, it was found that male teachers had higher perceptions in some dimensions (such as observation and oral presentation evaluation), but the difference between them and female teachers was generally small. Cingöz and Akyürek's (2021) finding that teachers found the contribution of assessment techniques to critical thinking skills insufficient may be associated with the low standard deviations of teachers in some assessment dimensions observed in our study. Especially low standard deviation in techniques such as project evaluation and product file evaluation may indicate that teachers offer less diversity in their evaluation processes. The findings of Karbeyaz (2018) and Yıldız and Genç (2016) on alternative assessment and evaluation techniques overlap with our study. In our study, it was observed that observation, oral presentation and performance assessment techniques were frequently used by teachers, but perceptions were lower for techniques such as project and product file. As in the literature, it is understood that diversity in the use of alternative assessment and evaluation techniques is limited. Işıkoğan's (2014) finding that male teachers have a more positive view of the constructivist approach is supported by the high perceptions of male teachers in constructivist assessment methods such as observation and oral presentation in our findings. Gündoğdu's (2012) findings indicating that traditional measurement tools are more preferred coincide with the results showing that some alternative methods (such as project and product file) are perceived less in our study. Çakmak's (2011) findings that gender and seniority do not make a significant difference in the level of use of alternative measurement techniques are partially compatible with the seniority and gender variables in our study. However, some differences were observed in perception levels depending on seniority, and it was determined that teachers with 16-20 years of seniority had more positive perceptions.

In conclusion, in this study, it was seen that factors such as gender, age, seniority, level of education and level of training in assessment and evaluation had different effects on teachers' perceptions. It was found that teachers in the younger age groups had higher perceptions in self-assessment and group assessment dimensions, and as seniority increased, perception levels decreased, but the diversity in perceptions decreased. In terms of educational level, small differences were found between undergraduate and graduate graduates in terms of perceptions, but it was observed that the diversity of perceptions was higher in graduate graduates. It was determined that teachers who received measurement and evaluation training generally had more positive perceptions, but this difference was often limited. The perception dimensions examined in the study were self-assessment, peer and group assessment, observation assessment, oral presentation assessment, project assessment and product file assessment. Small but significant differences emerged in these dimensions depending on teachers' demographic and professional characteristics. In general, the findings showed that teachers' perceptions were shaped by their professional experience, demographic characteristics and the education they received. These results provide important data for planning teachers' professional development programs and improving assessment and evaluation processes.

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